

Assessing Fishery Teachers' Improvement Needs To Train Secondary School Graduates For Self-Employment In Delta State

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria's education system has undergone significant changes over the years, shifting its focus towards skill training and curriculum realignment to meet the demands of a global economy and knowledge society. The new Senior Secondary School Trade Curriculum (SSTC) aims to equip students with functional trade and entrepreneurship skills making them employment – ready on graduation. This study was therefore designed to assess fishery teachers' improvement needs to train secondary school graduates for self-employment in Delta state, Nigeria. A total of 288 fishery teachers responded to a structured questionnaire which sought to determine their improvement needs in fishery using the Borich (1980) needs assessment model. Importance ratings and level of skill possession were determined using 4 point scale. Mean Weighted Discrepancy Scores were thereafter computed and used to rank their needs. Results showed that all the 50 technical skills suggested had positive MWDS, pointing towards high level of need among the teachers. The teachers' preferred seminars, workshops, conferences, symposia, long vacation courses and field trips/excursion as training modes. This paper recommends that the identified improvement needs in fishery be built into training modules by the Ministry of Education to provide the needed training using the preferred modes.

Keywords: Fishery teachers, improvement needs, secondary school graduates, self-employment.

INTRODUCTION

Fishery is a branch of agriculture that deals with the rearing of fish and other aquatic creatures for human use. It is the branch of agriculture that deals with the use of water to culture types of fish species (Madueke 2020, Olaitan & Omonia, 2009). Fish is an important source of food nutrients and contains up to 40% of protein consumed as diet by man (Asogwa, 2013, Brown 2017). It is an aquatic cold-blooded animal that lives in water body temperature fluctuates within the surrounding environment. It means that fish is naturally adapted to cold water. (Asogwa, 2013, Brown 2017). Besides, fish scales yield substances that could be coated as glues, beads, for decoration (Iwena, 2008). Consequently, Ogwu, Ikeoji and Nwakor (2021) affirmed that fish is an important component of human diet. It contains protein, carbohydrates, vitamins, minerals and fats.

The federal government through the federal ministry of education directed the inclusion of Fishery as a trade subject. The federal ministry of education (FME) directed the review of the curriculum of secondary schools, making fishery as a single subject in secondary schools. In response to the directive to the FME to develop senior secondary school curriculum on fishery as a trade, the objectives of the curriculum are as follows.

1. For students to have fishery as a trade for livelihood on completion of fish studies.
2. To protect fish that will increase the nutritive value of man's diet.
3. To be able to meet with the gap between demand and supply: and
4. To bridge the gap between poverty and hunger (NPE, 2013).

According to Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations (FAO, 2018), Ugolo (2017) and Nwanko (2018) fish farming leads to unemployment in importing countries and employment in exporting countries. The federal Government of Nigeria was enjoyed by individuals and corporate bodies to reduce youth unemployment by engaging them in vocational training and less emphasis on paper qualification in technical and vocational skills to rescue the country from its present youth's unemployment and economic decline. This is to further achieve the 2030 Sustainable Development Goal number four which clearly states that to "ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities". More specifically, target 4.4 emphasized that by 2030 there should be a substantial increase in the number of youths and adults who have relevant skills including technical and vocational skills for employment, decent jobs and entrepreneurship (U.N.O 2015).

According to the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN,2013,p.31), school-based agricultural education in Nigeria is intended to provide technical knowledge and vocational skills necessary for agriculture, commercial and economic development. It further stipulates that trainees on completing technical college programmes shall have three options which are to secure employment either at the end of the whole course or after completing one or more modules of employable skills, set up their own business and becoming self - employed and be able to employ others (...p.310). To further buttress this, Education Reforms (2004) stressed that this is consistent with Reforms in vocational education in secondary schools across the world of work and connecting the course content and pedagogy with local and international needs so as to develop an appropriate indigenous technology for development and social change.

Phipps et al (2008) stated purpose of agricultural education in schools to include (i) preparing people for entry or advancement in agricultural occupations and professions (ii) job creation and entrepreneurship; and (iii) agricultural literacy. However, a report by Gray and Herr in 2006 has it that 30% of high school graduates seeking employment were not provided the necessary skills in high school which has resulted in high unemployment. This is in consonance with the report in Nigeria as released by the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) (2010) that unemployment situation gets worse with increasing proportion of unskilled graduates at all levels of the educational system.

National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) report that unemployment in Nigeria increased to 33.30 per cent in the fourth quarter of 2020 from 27.10 per cent in the second quarter of 2020. Meanwhile, in a recent report by KPMG, the Nigerian unemployment rate had increased to 37.7 per cent in 2022 and would further rise to 40.6 per cent in 2023 due to the continuing in flow of job seekers into job market (Vanguard,2023).

Izuaka (2023) reported in Times that the NBS had in March 2021 had a record of Nigeria's unemployment rate risen to 33.3 per cent, translating to some 23.2 million people, the highest rate in the world. The figure jumped from 27.1 per cent recorded in the second quarter of 2020 amidst Nigeria's lingering economic crisis made worse by the coronavirus pandemic (covid-19).

Self-employment is the state of working for oneself rather than an employer. Tax authorities will generally view a person as self-employed if the person chooses to be recognized as such or if the person is generating income for which a tax return needs to be filled. Self-employed persons are the individuals who own sole or joint businesses of the unincorporated enterprises. It includes the unpaid family workers, outworkers and workers engaged in production for their own final consumption or own capital formation, either individually or collectively according to the European system of Accounts (ESA). The organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) describes the self-employed as the ones who own account worker or a person in production of goods and services and household consumption. Parker (2004) says they are individuals who earn no wage or salary but derive their income by completing their profession on their own account and at risk (Amaral and Batista,2006).

The new SSSTC introduced 34 Trade/ Entrepreneurship subjects among which is Fishery. Fishery is an offshoot of the traditional Agricultural Education subjects in senior secondary schools which purpose is to 'provide fishery vocation for those who are terminating at senior secondary schools education but will want to use the acquired skills and competences for later life (NERDC, 2007: p vi). Ikeoji (2018) recommended that these trade subjects are necessary for entry- level employment of graduates of senior secondary in (fishery) industry.

In response to engaging the youths in vocational and technical skills, the federal government introduced the new senior secondary school Trade curriculum (SSSTC) in senior secondary schools in 2013. NERDC stated

that the philosophy of the trade curriculum is that, on completion of the last three years of secondary education, every recipient would have been well prepared for higher education as well as acquired a vocational skill for wealth creation and hunger eradication (SSSTC,p5).

Ogwu et al (2020) described the trade curriculum as a paradigm shift from cognitive-centered education to psychomotor, as it is job creation and poverty eradication centered curriculum. Doherty (2019) opined that trade curriculum was designed to make Nigeria youths focus on job and wealth creation and thus reduce unemployment. Trade curriculum is a problem solving curriculum, which was adopted when youth's entrepreneurship to check heightened unemployment has become a global mandate and it is also opined that SSSTC adoption is apt and timely because it is designed as job and wealth creation document general towards achieving the united Nations sustainable development goals of poverty and hunger eradication. The trade curriculum involves 34 skills areas including Fishery.

Attempts at reaching the global problem of youth's unemployment have led to the introduction of skills acquisition in various countries of the world. In Nigeria, fishery was introduced into secondary school curriculum as a module of empowering youths to take fishery occupation on graduation. Pedagogy of fishery requires the teacher to be competent in the skills of fishery teaching.

Most teachers of agricultural science who are currently teaching fishery to students were trained before the introduction of fishery as a single subject. This implies that their preparation in the university may not have been in line with the new curriculum neither were they given any in - service training to improve their capacity in terms of technical information for effective implementation. This might be the reason for the student's inability to establish fish production as a trade on graduation after being exposed to curriculum content of fishery in the secondary schools. The introduction of the fishery trade curriculum without assessing the technical knowhow of the fishery expertise through in-service training has generated a lot of criticisms. It is quite worrisome that as soon as government directed the implementation of the subject, school, redeployed existing teachers who did not even specialize in agriculture to teach fishery trade subject. In most cases, the teachers compromised those who studied other branches of agriculture such as animal science, crop science, and soil science or agronomy including some of those who specialize in biology. Since teachers who presently teach the subject (fishery) are those who were trained many years ago, there is need to ascertain their competence to teach fishery based content in the schools. The reality is that due to improper planning in terms of staff training and development, fishery trade teachers in the Nigerian secondary schools may still be lacking in the requisite technical skills in Fishery (Asogwa,2013, Okafor and Ifeanyieze, 2014) as their pre-service training were inadequate in teaching practical skills in fishery instructions. Therefore, such teachers need improvement in their practical skills to do well in the classroom instructional delivery. Thus, this study seeks to asses fishery teachers improvement needs to train secondary school graduates for self-employment in Delta state.

Theoretical Framework

This study will be guided by the Human capital theory (HCT) as produced by the America Economist, Greg Becker in 1964. It argues that individual workers have a set of skills or abilities which they can improve or accumulate through training and education. It assesses the investment a person makes in his or her education skills, experiences and training (Becker, 1994, Little, 2008) for the purpose of employability. The theory posits that human beings can increase in their productive capacity through greater education and skills training. It emphasizes how education increases the productivity and efficiency of workers (including teachers) by increasing the level of cognitive stock of economically productive human capability, which is a product innate abilities and investment human beings. It posits that by emphasizing education and training, workers can become more productive and efficient. As a result, components such as education, effective communication skills, management of people, training at work, the ability to solve problems, personal health and wellbeing are the components that are part of Human Capital Theory. It rest on the assumption that formal education is highly instrumental and necessary to improve the productive capacity of the population.

The theory is about the idea of humans increasing their productivity and efficiency through a greater focus on education. According to Ikeoji (2018), the SSSTC as published by NERDC(2007) is consistent with HCT and was designed to meet the targets of the National Economic Empowerment and development Strategy (NEEDS), which was expressed as value-orientations, poverty education, job creation, wealth generation and using education to empower the citizenry. Ikeoji (2018) reiterated the emphasis of Roberts and Ball (2009) that

teachers should provide industry-relevant instruction that results in observable skill acquisition to ensure that students acquire technical skills and competencies that enable them enter into occupation as well as gain successful employment for livelihood.

Fig 1. A coceptual mode Adapted from Robert and Ball (2009)and Ikeoji (2018)

Purpose/ Objectives

The main purpose of this study was to assess fishery teachers' improvement needs to train secondary school graduates for self-employment in Delta State. More specifically, the study seeks to;

- 1) determine the importance ratings of required technical and pedagogical skills as established by fishery teachers in secondary schools for self-employment of graduates.
- 2) determine the extent to which fishery teachers possess the required technical pedagogical skills to train secondary school fishery graduates for self-employment in Delta State.
- 3) determine and prioritize improvement needs of the teachers using the Mean Weighted Discrepancy Scores as prescribed by Borich (1980)
- 4) Determine the different training modes preferred by the teachers for improvement.

METHODOLOGY

The target population for the study consists of secondary school teachers of fishery as a trade subject in public schools in Delta State. To address the research objectives, the study will utilize an instrument constructed in line with Borich's (1980) approach to needs assessment to assess the teacher's perceived level of importance and perceived level of competence regarding identified technical and pedagogical skills. The instrument will consist of two parts: (a) items requesting for personal demographic and professional characteristics (b) Identified technical and pedagogical skills required and instrument which will enable the teachers to indicate (i) their assessment of how important they considered the skills, and (ii) the level of possession of such skills in the teaching of fishery as a trade subject. The scale for the importance rating will be rated on a 4-point scale ranging from 1= not important to 4= very important while that of possession rating will also be on a 4- point scale ranging from 1= not possessed to 4= highly possessed. Data collected in respect of teacher's demographic and professional instruction will be analyzed using simple frequency counts and percentages and presented in tables. Data collected from rating scales will be analyzed using means. A mean weighted Discrepancy Score (MWDS) will be calculated to describe the overall rankings for each of the competencies. To determine the MWDS, a discrepancy score will be calculated for each competency by subtracting the importance ratings from the ability (competency) ratings. A weighted discrepancy score will then be calculated on each individual for each of the technical and pedagogical skills by multiplying the discrepancy score by the mean importance rating. That is, a mean weighted discrepancy score for each of the competencies will be calculated by taking the sum of the discrepancy scores, the competencies will then be ranked. (Zarafshan & Alibagi, 2008; Garton & Chung, 1997; Newman & Johnson, 1994; Barrick et al, 1983; Borich, 1980; Ikeoji, 2018). If the importance value according to Ikeoji (2018) is higher than the level of possession, it will result in a positive MWDS and indicates a need for further training, while a negative MWDS indicates that level of skills possession meets or is in excess of the needs of teachers.

Table 1 : Ranking of Training/ Technical Skills Needed by Fishery Teachers with Regards to the implementation of the Fishery Trade Curriculum Based on Mean Weighted Discrepancy Scores (n= 188)

S/N	Training/ Technical Skills	Importance Mean	Possession Mean	Discrepancy Sore	MDWS Priority	by Ranking
1	Broodstock selection	3.72	2.17	1.55	5.77	1 st
2	Artificial breeding and management	3.70	2.18	1.54	5.69	2 nd
3	Stripping of gravid female	3.75	2.25	1.50	5.63	3 rd
4	Mixing of milt and ovaries	3.71	2.20	1.51	5.60	4 th
5	Nursery fish feeding	3.43	1.82	1.61	5.52	5 th
6	Pond preparation and management	3.58	2.05	1.53	5.48	6 th
7	Impoundment of pond (filling of pond with water	3.49	1.93	1.56	5.44	7 th
8	Pond liming procedures	3.68	2.21	1.47	5.41	8 th
9	Pond fertilizing	3.82	2.42	1.40	5.36	9 th
10	Monitoring water quality	3.54	2.05	1.49	5.28	10 th
11	Measurement of dissolved oxygen with Wrinklers's method	3.78	2.40	1.38	5.23	11 th
12	Pond temperature measurement	3.33	1.77	1.56	5.19	12 th
13	Measurement of pond turbidity	3.46	1.88	1.58	5.14	13 th
14	Fish ration formulation	3.40	1.90	1.50	5.09	14 th
15	Identification of disease of fish	3.17	1.58	1.59	5.04	15 th
16	Pest control and fish health management	3.19	1.62	1.57	5.01	16 th
17	Operating nets (cast nets, seine nets, gill nets)	3.65	2.28	1.37	5.00	17 th
18	Stocking of pond with fingerlings	3.28	1.78	1.50	4.92	18 th
19	Maintaining pond water quality	3.87	2.62	1.25	4.84	19 th
20	Identify fish ingredients for fish ration formulation	3.88	2.64	1.24	4.81	20 th
21	Construction of fishing tools	3.80	2.54	1.26	4.79	21 st
22	Identify male and female reproductive organs	3.29	1.86	1.43	4.70	22 nd
23	Regular harvesting/sorting	3.11	1.61	1.43	4.67	23 rd
24	Constant supply of water	4.08	2.96	1.12	4.57	24 th
25	Vaccinate fish for disease prevention	2.95	1.47	1.48	4.37	25 th
26	Identify common endo and ecto parasites of fish	2.71	1.70	1.01	2.74	26 th
27	Determine and Identify fish with ripe ovaries	3.18	2.36	0.82	2.61	27 th
28	Reading acidity and alkalinity of pond water using P ^H meter	3.36	2.59	0.77	2.59	28 th
29	Check level of acidity using litmus paper	3.43	2.70	0.73	2.55	29 th
30	Aeration	2.92	2.03	0.89	2.54	30 th
31	Identify symptoms of malnutrition in fish	2.94	2.02	0.92	2.52	31 st
32	Identify diseased fish	2.64	1.69	0.95	2.51	32 nd
33	Identify fish for culling	3.25	2.48	0.77	2.50	33 rd

34	Identify symptoms of fish disease	3.16	2.37	0.79	2.50	34 th
35	Deweeding	3.18	2.40	0.78	2.48	35 th
36	Control of predators	3.07	2.27	0.80	2.45	36 th
37	Maintain appropriate pond hygiene	3.81	3.17	0.64	2.44	37 th
38	Use of fishing tools	3.23	2.49	0.74	2.39	38 th
39	Estimate male/female ration in fish breeding systems	3.76	3.14	0.62	2.33	39 th
40	Identify different stages of growth of fish	3.37	2.70	0.67	2.26	40 th
41	Identify feedstuffs with various nutritional compounds	3.54	2.91	2.91	0.63	41 st
42	Maintain appropriate pond hygiene	3.74	3.16	0.58	2.18	42 nd
43	Feeding of fish	3.49	2.88	0.61	2.13	43 rd
44	Prevention and control of pond water pollution	3.76	3.20	0.56	2.11	44 th
45	Partial harvesting	3.39	2.69	0.69	2.10	45 th
46	Post-harvesting processing	3.30	2.67	0.63	2.08	46 th
47	Keep basic management records	3.38	2.78	0.60	2.03	47 th
48	Preservation of fish such as smoking, freezing icing, canning, salting and sun drying	3.64	3.09	0.55	2.00	48 th
49	Marketing of fish and fish products	3.89	3.40	0.49	1.91	49 th
50	Total harvesting	3.82	3.33	0.49	1.8	50 th

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Results in table 1 show that all 50 technical skills identified in respondents had positive MWDS ranging from 1.82 to 5.77. Seventeen of such skills with the greatest needs for further training were; (1) broodstock selection (MWDS=5.77);(2) artificial breeding and management (MWDS=5.69; (3) stripping of gravid female (MWDS=5.63); (4) mixing of milt and ovaries (MWDS= 5.60; (5) nursery fish feeding (MWDS, 5.52); (6) pond preparation and management (MWDS=5.48); (7) impoundment of pond (MWDS= 5.44); (8) Pond liming procedures(MWDS=5.41); (9) pond fertilization (MWDS=5.36); (10) monitoring water quality (MWDS=5.28); (11) measurement of dissolved oxygen (MWDS=5.23); (12) pond temperature measurement (MWDS= 5.19); (13) MWDS of 5.14 on measurement of pond turbidity; (14) the responses from fishery teachers on fish ration formulation showed their MWDS to be 5.09; (15) identification of diseases of fish (MWDS= 5.04); (16) pest control and fish health management (MWDS= 5.01); (17) Responses have MWDS of 5.00 on operating nets. Three technical skills recorded the least MWDS, indicating no need for training as follows; preservation of fish (MWDS=1.96); marketing of fish and fish products (MWDS=1.91) and; total harvesting (MWDS=1.87).

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The results showed that all of the 50 technical skills had positive MWDS, pointing toward high level of need among teachers. According to Roberts and Ball (2009) in Ikeoji (2018), the identified technical needs were consistent with expectations in the new (trade) curriculum which “ should reflect the needs of the industry”. 34 of the 50 technical skills are within the accepted average of 2.50 and above. Furthermore, seventeen technical needs with the greatest needs as expressed training needs by fishery teachers are broodstock selection, artificial breeding and management, stripping of gravid female, mixing

of milt and ovaries, nursery fish and feeding, pond preparation and management, impoundment of pond fertilization, monitoring water quality, measurement of dissolved oxygen with Wrinkler's method, pond temperature measurement, measurement of pond turbidity, fish ration formulation, identification of diseases of fish, pests control and fish health management and operating nets (casts nets , seine nets, gill nets). It is important to note that this study is in line with the findings of Asogwa (2016) who identified broodstock selection, artificial breeding and management and nursery fish feeding as technical information needs of teachers of agricultural science on fishery for effective teaching of students in senior secondary schools in Enugu state. Furthermore, the findings of this study corroborate that of Ogwu et al (2021) on skill gaps and training needs of teachers for effective implementation of senior secondary schools trade curriculum in fishery in Delta state. The findings identified deficiencies in operating nets such as cast nets, seine nets and gill nets, measurement of dissolved oxygen with wrinkler's method, pond temperature measurement, measurement of pond turbidity, pond liming, pond fertilization, stripping of gravid female and fish health management. Ikeoji (2018) also identified technical skills needed by animal husbandry teachers to include; vaccinate animals for disease prevention, identify symptoms of animal diseases, recognize common endo and ecto parasites, carry out artificial insemination, determine and identify pregnant females, identify ingredients for ration formulation; and identify birds/ livestock for culling.

The findings from this research on the preferred type of training modes of in-service programme showed that fishery teachers expressed a strong desire for professional development through various training opportunities to enhance their knowledge and skills through continuous training and capacity-building programmes such as seminars, conferences, workshops, internship, long vacation courses, symposia, full-time courses at the universities and other tertiary institutions, field-trips/ excursions and distance learning. Ikeoji(2018) reported that animal husbandry teachers preferred short duration vacation training, workshops, conferences and engagement of accredited livestock farmers for school demonstration as training modes. According to Ogwu (2017), fishery teachers are willing to undergo training on- the- job and seminars. Akpomedaye 92016) highlighted field-trips and professional organisations. Idolor et al (2022) showed that teachers can undergo long vacation courses and group interaction as ways of achieving capacity- building of agricultural education teachers.

CONCLUSION

Nigeria's senior secondary school fishery trade curriculum aims to empower students with practical skills for self-employment and wealth creation in fisheries and aquaculture industry. This focus is on equipping students with functional skills to establish and manage their own fishery enterprises, thereby promoting sustainability and vocationalism in the sector. Now that teachers are aware of the curriculum's rationale and philosophy, the priority is to ensure its effective implementation and sustainability, enabling school graduates to earn a living and contribute meaningfully to their society. The challenges in delivering fishery education as a vocational/trade curriculum is rooted in a combination of fundamental factors such as teacher capacity (lack of relevant knowledge and skills), human resources (inadequate manpower) and infrastructure (insufficient facilities and equipment).

The success of the trade curriculum depends on teachers capacity-building through in-service training, on-the-job training, conferences and workshops. Without ongoing development opportunities, teachers' knowledge gaps in fishery will directly impact student's skills acquisition, compromising the curriculum's objectives and undermining its potential impact.

Effective implementation of the fishery trade curriculum in Nigeria particularly in Delta state hinges on empowering teachers with the necessary knowledge and skills. This is crucial for reducing youth unemployment and promoting conducive working environments (creating an optional setting for teachers to thrive), recruiting certified fishery teachers (erasing workload on existing teachers and ensuring specialized expertise), enhanced salary scales (motivating teachers with competitive compensation) and in-service training (offering ongoing professional development opportunities). By investing in teacher development and productivity, Nigeria can improve fishery education quality, enhance student's skills

acquisition, reduce youth unemployment and boost economic growth through fishery production. Ultimately, making fishery teachers the centre piece of this trade curriculum will enhance their productivity, reduce systemic problems and ensure effective service delivery.

Proper funding of agriculture-based institutions by the government is crucial for achieving policy objectives such as youth empowerment, job and wealth creation, poverty reduction and food security in Delta State as well as Nigeria as a whole. This funding can be boosted through collaboration with agriculture entrepreneurs (including fishery entrepreneurs) who can provide valuable support in funding and managing trade and skills acquisition programmes in secondary schools.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In light of the findings and conclusions made from the study, the following strategic recommendations are hereby proposed:

1. Regular in-service training programmes such as workshops and seminars should be organized for teachers who are teaching fishery to gain more knowledge on modern fishery practices
2. Fishery teachers should undergo capacity- building on entrepreneurship and business management.
3. There should be pedagogy training and mentorship programmes for new fishery teachers for effective teaching
4. Fishery teachers and school authorities should develop partnerships with private sector (such as fish entrepreneurs) for facility utilization
5. In regards to the skill gaps identified in this study, teachers should be given opportunities for short-term training programmes in aquaculture and fish farm management, fisheries conservation and management, aquatic food processing and management, entrepreneurship and business planning and information and communication technology (ICT) skills; and long-term capacity building such as degree programmes in fishery science or aquaculture, post graduate certifications in specialized areas (such as aquaculture and fisheries management) and fellowship and research grants for advanced studies.
6. Successful implementation of the trade curriculum hinges on the supervisory body's ability to provide effective coordination, supervision and quality control, thereby ensuring the achievement of the curriculum's goals.

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